

«New Concept of Extended Strings and Their Role in the Universe»

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Abstract

In this paper, we propose a new concept that combines the ideas of string theory with our view of large-scale strings that stretch across the entire Universe. We consider strings not as extremely small objects, but as large structures that form the "fabric" of the Universe. These strings are carriers of energy and vibrations that create all known particles. We discuss the interaction of strings with light, the role of black holes, and the balancing of planetary systems. Additionally, we assume that cosmic anomalies can be seen as errors in the vibrational modes of these strings. The dual nature of particles and waves can be interpreted as different vibrational or resonance states of these extended strings.

We also introduce a hypothesis about dark matter, suggesting that it represents regions devoid of fundamental strings. Furthermore, we explore the concept of inter-string space, which contributes to the understanding of the structure and expansion of the Universe.

Our theory is based on the fundamental principles of quantum mechanics and string theory, including the works of John Schwarz and Michael Green, who initiated modern string theory. We also rely on the ideas of the holographic principle proposed by Gerard 't Hooft and developed by Leonard Susskind, and the concepts of quantum entanglement investigated by Albert Einstein, Boris Podolsky, and Nathan Rosen. This theory aims to provide a new perspective on the structure and expansion of the Universe and seeks collaboration for further development and mathematical substantiation.

Introduction

Modern physics, particularly string theory and quantum mechanics, provides a foundation for understanding the Universe on the smallest scales. String theory, proposed by John Schwarz and Michael Green, posits that all elementary particles are vibrational states of one-dimensional "strings." This unifies quantum mechanics and general relativity, two fundamental theories of physics. However, many aspects remain unresolved.

We propose a new concept that strings are not confined to Planck-scale sizes but stretch from the moment of the Big Bang, forming the basic structure of the Universe. These extended strings carry vibrational modes that manifest as particles and influence the formation and stability of cosmic structures. Our theory also incorporates the holographic principle proposed by Gerard 't Hooft and developed by Leonard Susskind, which states that all information in space can be encoded on its boundary. We consider inter-string space as a region with unique properties that contributes to the overall dynamics of the Universe.

This paper aims to:

- Consider strings as large structures forming the foundation of the Universe.
- Study the interaction of strings with light and other particles.
- Explain the dual nature of particles and waves through the vibrational states of strings.
- Explore inter-string space and its impact on the structure and expansion of the Universe.
- Propose a new perspective on dark matter as regions devoid of fundamental strings.
- Examine the correction of errors in the Universe through string mechanisms.
- Explain the balancing of planetary systems using strings.
- Investigate the role of black holes in the context of our theory.

We hope our theory provides new insights into the structure and expansion of the Universe and invites the scientific community to further research and discussion.

Main Ideas

Extended Strings as Fundamental Components

Traditional string theory states that all elementary particles are vibrational states of one-dimensional "strings" with extremely small sizes on the order of the Planck length (approximately 10^{-35} meters). However, we propose a new concept that these strings can be extended to much larger scales, forming a kind of "fabric" of the Universe.

In our theory, extended strings stretch from the moment of the Big Bang and form the basic structure of the Universe. They act as carriers of energy and vibrations that create all known particles. Each particle we observe is the result of the vibrational mode of these strings. Consequently, the properties of particles such as mass and charge are determined by the vibrational characteristics of the strings.

Extended strings can also interact with each other, forming complex structures and networks. These interactions create the basis for more complex cosmic phenomena such as gravitational fields, electromagnetic waves, and other fundamental forces of nature.

Main Properties of Extended Strings:

- **Size and Stretch:** Extended strings are not confined to Planck scales but stretch throughout the Universe, forming its basic structure.
- **Vibrational Modes:** Each string has different vibrational modes that manifest as particles with different properties (mass, charge, spin, etc.).
- **String Networks:** Strings can interact with each other, forming complex networks. These networks are the basis for the emergence and stabilization of cosmic structures.
- **Energy and Information:** Strings are carriers of energy and information. The vibrational states of strings can encode information about the structure and dynamics of the Universe.

Interaction of Extended Strings with Other Elements of the Universe:

- **Gravitational Fields:** The vibrational states of strings can create gravitational fields that warp space-time and determine the movement of massive objects.
- **Electromagnetic Waves:** Strings can interact with electromagnetic waves, changing their intensity and direction.
- **Black Holes:** In our theory, black holes can be considered as regions where strings lose their vibrational modes. This creates strong gravitational fields that absorb everything, including light.
- **Dark Matter:** We assume that dark matter can represent regions devoid of fundamental strings. This creates specific gravitational anomalies that we observe as the influence of dark matter.

Influence of Extended Strings on Cosmic Phenomena:

- **Formation of Galaxies and Stars:** The interaction of strings can explain the processes of galaxy and star formation. Strings create gravitational fields that gather mass and form cosmic structures.

- **Expansion of the Universe:** Extended strings can influence the dynamics of the expansion of the Universe, ensuring its stability and uniformity.
- **Cosmic Anomalies:** Cosmic phenomena such as galaxy collisions or black hole formation can be the result of string interactions and errors in their vibrational modes.

Our approach to considering strings as large structures allows us to take a new look at fundamental questions of physics and cosmology. Further research in this direction can open new horizons in the study of the Universe and contribute to a deeper understanding of its structure and dynamics.

Interaction of Strings with Light

In our theory, light is considered as vibrations of strings. Photons, which are quanta of light, can be interpreted as specific vibrational modes of these strings. This means that light can propagate along strings, explaining its behavior even in the presence of black holes.

Properties of Interaction of Strings with Light:

- **Vibrational Modes:** Each string has several vibrational modes that can manifest as photons with different energies. This explains the wide spectrum of light frequencies from radio waves to gamma rays.
- **Wave-Particle Duality:** According to quantum mechanics, light can manifest as both a particle and a wave. In the context of our theory, this can be explained by the fact that the vibrational modes of strings have both wave and particle properties. For example, when a photon interacts with other particles or passes through narrow slits, it exhibits particle properties. When it propagates through space, it behaves like a wave.
- **Gravitational Lensing:** Strings can create gravitational fields that warp the trajectories of light. This phenomenon is known as gravitational lensing. Gravitational lenses occur when light from distant stars or galaxies is warped by the gravity of massive objects such as galaxy clusters. In our theory, this can be explained by the fact that strings create gravitational fields that warp the trajectories of light.

Interaction of Light with Strings:

- **Absorption and Emission:** When light interacts with a string, it can be absorbed and converted into the vibrational state of the string. Later, the string can emit light when it changes its vibrational mode. This explains phenomena such as the photoelectric effect and the emission of spectral lines.
- **Light in the Presence of Black Holes:** According to general relativity, black holes have such strong gravitational fields that even light cannot escape them. In our theory, this is explained by the fact that black holes are regions where strings lose their vibrational modes that correspond to light. This is consistent with quantum field theory, where black holes can absorb and store information about particles.
- **Propagation of Light:** Light can propagate along strings that penetrate space. This explains why light can travel long distances in space without significant energy loss. The interaction of light with strings can also explain some anomalous observations such as anomalies in the redshift of distant galaxies.

Our approach to studying the interaction of strings with light offers a new perspective on the nature of light and its properties. Further research in this direction can open new opportunities for understanding fundamental physical phenomena and contribute to the development of new technologies in optics and quantum physics.

Dual Nature of Particles and Waves

The dual nature of particles and waves is one of the fundamental principles of quantum mechanics. According to this principle, elementary particles such as electrons, photons, and others can exhibit properties of both particles and waves, depending on the experimental conditions. This phenomenon is known as wave-particle duality.

Explanation of Dual Nature in the Context of Our Theory:

- **Vibrational States of Strings:** In our theory, each particle is a vibrational mode of a string. These vibrations can exhibit wave properties (e.g., interference and diffraction) or particle properties (e.g., localized interactions with detectors).
- **Transition Between Modes:** The vibrational modes of strings can change depending on external conditions, allowing particles to exhibit different properties. For example, in the case of interference experiments, strings can vibrate in wave mode, creating interference patterns. At the same time, in the case of interactions with detectors, strings can transition to particle mode, exhibiting localized properties.
- **Quantum Entanglement:** The concept of quantum entanglement also finds its explanation in our theory. Entangled particles can be considered as strings that interact over long distances. The vibrational states of one string can instantly affect the states of another string, explaining the phenomena of quantum entanglement.

Examples of Dual Nature of Particles and Waves:

- **Electrons in Diffraction Experiments:** Electrons can create diffraction patterns when passing through two slits, demonstrating their wave properties. At the same time, when interacting with detectors, they exhibit particle properties, creating localized traces on the detector.
- **Photons in Interferometric Experiments:** Photons can create interference patterns in experiments with interferometers, demonstrating wave properties. At the same time, when detected, they exhibit particle properties.
- **Quantum Teleportation:** In quantum teleportation, information about the quantum state of one particle is transmitted to another particle over a long distance. In our theory, this can be explained by the interaction between strings that are in a quantum entangled state.

Interaction of Wave and Particle Properties:

- **Superposition:** The vibrational states of strings can be in a state of superposition, where a particle simultaneously has several possible states. This explains phenomena such as quantum superposition, where a particle can be in several states simultaneously.

- **Wave Function Collapse:** In our theory, the collapse of the wave function occurs as a transition of the vibrational state of the string from wave mode to particle mode. This explains why a quantum object exhibits a definite state when measured.

Our approach to explaining the dual nature of particles and waves allows us to combine wave and particle properties in a single theory. This provides new opportunities for understanding the fundamental principles of quantum mechanics and can contribute to the development of new experimental methods in quantum physics.

Inter-String Space

Inter-string space is an important element of our theory, which considers the interaction and dynamics of strings in the Universe. This space can be considered as the region between individual strings, which has its unique properties and plays a key role in the structure and expansion of the Universe.

Properties of Inter-String Space:

- **Spatial Structure:** Inter-string space has a complex and multilayered structure that can vary depending on the interaction of strings. This structure can affect the propagation of energy and matter in the Universe.
- **Energy Properties:** Inter-string space can be a source or absorber of energy, depending on the vibrational states of strings. This can explain some cosmic phenomena such as dark energy and its impact on the expansion of the Universe.
- **Impact on Particles:** Particles passing through inter-string space may undergo changes in their properties such as mass, charge, or spin. This may be the result of interaction with the vibrational modes of the strings that form this space.

Role of Inter-String Space in the Formation and Development of the Universe:

- **Formation of Structures:** Inter-string space can contribute to the formation of galaxies, stars, and planets by providing the necessary conditions for gravitational condensation and accretion of matter. The interaction of strings in inter-string space can create gravitational fields that gather and concentrate mass, forming cosmic objects.
- **Expansion of the Universe:** Inter-string space can influence the dynamics of the expansion of the Universe. The interaction of strings and their vibrational modes can create additional pressure that promotes the uniform expansion of the Universe. This can explain the observed accelerated expansion often attributed to dark energy.
- **Anomalous Phenomena:** Some cosmic anomalies, such as gravitational lenses or dark matter, may be the result of specific properties of inter-string space. The interaction of light and matter with this space can create effects that we observe as anomalous.

Possible Experimental Studies of Inter-String Space:

- **Space Telescopes:** Observations of distant galaxies and quasars can provide information about the properties of inter-string space. Analysis of gravitational lenses and redshift can help identify the impact of this space on the propagation of light.

- **Particle Accelerators:** Experiments on particle accelerators such as the Large Hadron Collider can provide data on the interaction of particles with inter-string space. Observations of anomalies in particle interactions can confirm or refute our theory.
- **Astrophysical Observations:** Studies of cosmic microwave background radiation and its anisotropies can provide information about the impact of inter-string space on the early stages of the development of the Universe.

Our approach to studying inter-string space allows us to expand the understanding of the structure and dynamics of the Universe. Further research in this direction can open new opportunities for studying fundamental physical phenomena and contribute to the development of new theories in cosmology and quantum physics.

Dark Matter

Dark matter remains one of the greatest mysteries of modern physics and cosmology. It does not interact with electromagnetic radiation, making it invisible to modern telescopes. However, its presence is revealed through the gravitational influence on visible matter, stars, and galaxies. In our theory, we propose a new explanation for the nature of dark matter.

Explanation of Dark Matter in the Context of Our Theory:

- **Absence of Fundamental Strings:** We assume that dark matter can represent regions of space devoid of fundamental strings. These "gaps" in the network of strings create specific gravitational anomalies that we observe as the influence of dark matter. In such regions, ordinary particles cannot exist because the vibrational modes of strings that form them are absent.
- **Gravitational Effects:** The interaction between regions containing strings and regions where strings are absent can create additional gravitational effects. This explains why dark matter has a significant gravitational influence, although its nature remains undefined. Dark matter can act as a kind of "gravitational shadow" in the Universe.
- **Energy State:** The absence of strings in certain regions can create a specific energy state that affects the properties of the surrounding space. This can explain some observed properties of dark matter such as its stability and immobility relative to ordinary matter.

Impact of Dark Matter on the Structure of the Universe:

- **Formation of Galaxies and Clusters:** Dark matter plays a key role in the formation and evolution of galaxies and galaxy clusters. The gravitational anomalies created by the absence of strings can promote the condensation of matter and the formation of large cosmic structures.
- **Impact on the Expansion of the Universe:** The gravitational influence of dark matter can affect the dynamics of the expansion of the Universe. Its presence can explain the observed accelerated expansion often attributed to dark energy.
- **Anomalies in Star Motion:** Observations of star motion in galaxies show that the rotational speed of stars on the periphery of galaxies is much higher than predicted by classical gravity theory. This phenomenon can be explained by the presence of dark matter, which creates additional gravitational forces.

Possible Experimental Studies of Dark Matter:

- **Astrophysical Observations:** Observations of the motion of galaxies, galaxy clusters, and gravitational lenses can provide additional evidence in favor of our theory. Analysis of these data can help determine the distribution of dark matter in the Universe.
- **Space Telescopes:** Using space telescopes such as Hubble and James Webb can provide new data on the interaction of dark matter with visible matter. This can help refine our models and test the hypothesis about the absence of strings in dark matter.
- **Laboratory Experiments:** Experiments on particle accelerators such as the Large Hadron Collider can provide information about the interaction of particles with regions devoid of strings. This can help confirm or refute our theory about the nature of dark matter.

Our theory proposes a new approach to understanding dark matter, considering it as regions of space devoid of fundamental strings. This provides new opportunities for studying its properties and impact on the structure of the Universe. Further research in this direction can contribute to the development of new theories and experimental methods in cosmology and quantum physics.

Error Correction

We assume that extended strings play a key role in stabilizing and correcting errors in the structure of the Universe. This correction mechanism allows maintaining the stability of cosmic structures and ensuring the gradual development of the Universe.

Mechanisms of Error Correction:

- **Stabilization of Vibrational Modes:** Strings can stabilize their vibrational modes, preventing the occurrence of chaotic oscillations. This ensures the stability of particles and cosmic objects. If strings in a certain region start to vibrate unstably, neighboring strings can interact with them and restore stable modes.
- **String Interaction:** Strings can interact with each other, creating networks that help correct errors. If the vibrational mode of one string changes due to external influences, other strings can change their modes to compensate for these changes and restore stability.
- **Gravitational Influences:** Strings can create gravitational fields that help stabilize the orbits of planets, stars, and galaxies. These gravitational influences can correct the trajectories of objects and prevent their collision or dispersion.

Examples of Error Correction in the Universe:

- **Expansion of the Universe:** We assume that the expansion of the Universe is corrected by strings that stabilize the system and correct errors. Major cosmic events such as galaxy collisions can be the result of small errors in the vibrational modes of strings that affect the structure of the Universe. Strings act as a correction mechanism, ensuring stability and gradual development of cosmic structures.
- **Cosmic Catastrophes:** Cases of cosmic catastrophes such as supernova explosions or black hole collisions can be the result of significant errors in the vibrational modes of

strings. However, these catastrophes can also be a mechanism by which the Universe corrects its errors, restoring stability after the destruction of old structures and the formation of new ones.

- **Balancing Planetary Systems:** The arrangement of planets in our solar system can be explained by the interaction of strings that create gravitational fields and stabilize systems. This allows maintaining balance and preventing catastrophic events. The interaction of strings ensures the stability of planetary orbits and regulates gravitational influences, creating conditions for the existence of life.

Possible Experimental Confirmations of Correction Mechanisms:

- **Observation of Cosmic Phenomena:** Observations of major cosmic events such as galaxy collisions or supernova explosions can provide information about correction mechanisms. Analyzing these events can help understand how strings stabilize the Universe after significant disturbances.
- **Computer Modeling:** Modeling the interaction of strings on cosmic scales can provide insights into how strings correct errors and maintain the stability of the Universe. Computer models can simulate the vibrational modes of strings and their interaction, providing valuable data for testing the theory.
- **Laboratory Experiments:** Studies of particle interactions in accelerators such as the Large Hadron Collider can provide information about correction mechanisms on a microscopic level. Observations of anomalies in particle interactions can confirm or refute our theory about error correction through strings.

Our theory of error correction proposes a new approach to understanding the stability and evolution of the Universe. Further research in this direction can contribute to the development of new theories and experimental methods in cosmology and quantum physics.

Balancing Planetary Systems

The arrangement and stability of planetary systems are important aspects of our understanding of the Universe. In our theory, we propose that strings play a key role in creating and maintaining this balance. Strings create gravitational fields that influence the orbits of planets and ensure the stability of cosmic structures.

Explanation of Balancing Planetary Systems in the Context of Our Theory:

- **Gravitational Fields of Strings:** Strings create gravitational fields that influence the arrangement of planets in planetary systems. These fields ensure the stability of planetary orbits, preventing their chaotic movement and collisions. The interaction of gravitational fields of strings forms a dynamic balance in systems such as our solar system.
- **Vibrational Modes:** The vibrations of strings can influence the orbits of planets, creating resonance effects. These resonances can stabilize planetary orbits, preventing them from deviating from stable trajectories. The vibrational modes of strings can also explain phenomena such as resonances between the orbits of planets and moons.
- **Adaptive Stability:** Strings can adapt their vibrational modes in response to changes in planetary systems. This provides flexibility and resilience of systems to external

influences such as asteroid collisions or changes in gravitational fields due to the movement of neighboring stars.

Examples of Balancing Planetary Systems:

- **Solar System:** The arrangement of planets in our solar system can be explained by the interaction of strings that create gravitational fields and stabilize the orbits of planets. For example, Jupiter, the largest planet in the solar system, creates a significant gravitational influence that stabilizes the orbits of other planets and protects the inner planets from collisions with comets and asteroids.
- **Resonances in the Jupiter System:** The orbits of some of Jupiter's moons are in resonance with each other. This phenomenon can be explained by the vibrational modes of strings that stabilize the orbits of these moons and prevent their deviation.
- **Exoplanetary Systems:** Observations of exoplanets in other star systems show that many of them have stable orbits, which may be the result of the interaction of strings. The gravitational fields of strings can stabilize the orbits of exoplanets and create conditions for the existence of life.

Possible Experimental Confirmations of Balancing Mechanisms:

- **Observations of Exoplanets:** Astrophysical observations of exoplanets can provide data on the stability of their orbits and interaction with gravitational fields. Analyzing these data can confirm or refute our theory about the role of strings in balancing planetary systems.
- **Computer Modeling:** Modeling the interaction of strings and planetary systems can provide insights into the mechanisms of orbit stabilization. Computer models can simulate the impact of gravitational fields of strings on planets and help test our hypotheses.
- **Study of the Solar System:** Detailed observations and analysis of the dynamics of planets and moons in our solar system can provide information about the gravitational influences of strings. This may include analyzing orbits, resonances, and the overall stability of the system.

Our theory offers a new perspective on balancing planetary systems, considering the role of strings in creating and maintaining the stability of planetary orbits and cosmic objects. Further research in this direction can contribute to the development of new theories and experimental methods in cosmology and astrophysics.

Role of Black Holes

Black holes are some of the most mysterious and important objects in the Universe. They arise from the collapse of massive stars, forming regions of space-time with such strong gravity that even light cannot escape them. In the context of our extended string theory, black holes can play a key role in the stabilization and evolution of the Universe.

Explanation of the Role of Black Holes in the Context of Our Theory:

- **Nodes in the Structure of Strings:** Black holes can be considered as nodes in the structure of strings where energy condensation occurs. In these nodes, strings lose their vibrational modes corresponding to light, creating regions with extremely high gravity.

- **Information Preservation:** According to quantum field theory, black holes can absorb and store information about particles. In our theory, this can be explained as the preservation of the vibrational modes of strings in the nodes of black holes. This information can be stored in the form of vibrational states of strings, even if it cannot be directly observed.
- **Energy Transitions:** Black holes can act as sites of energy transitions where energy from collapsing stars and other cosmic objects is converted into the vibrational modes of strings. This can explain phenomena such as Hawking radiation, where black holes emit particles and energy.

Impact of Black Holes on the Structure of the Universe:

- **Formation of Galaxies:** Black holes play a key role in the formation and evolution of galaxies. They can act as centers of gravitational attraction, gathering mass and contributing to the formation of galaxies. In our theory, this can be explained as the interaction of strings in the nodes of black holes that create gravitational fields and stabilize galaxies.
- **Active Galactic Nuclei:** Many galaxies have active nuclei that emit enormous amounts of energy. This phenomenon can be explained by the presence of massive black holes at the centers of these galaxies. The vibrational states of strings in these black holes can create powerful gravitational and electromagnetic fields that cause radiation.
- **Cosmic Phenomena:** Black holes can explain many cosmic phenomena such as gravitational waves that form during the merging of black holes. These waves can be considered as the vibrational modes of strings that transmit information about the interaction of black holes in space-time.

Possible Experimental Confirmations of the Role of Black Holes:

- **Gravitational Waves:** The discovery of gravitational waves caused by the merging of black holes confirms the important role of black holes in the structure of the Universe. Further observations of gravitational waves can provide new data on the vibrational states of strings in black holes.
- **Observations of Active Galactic Nuclei:** Studies of active galactic nuclei can provide information about the interaction of strings in black holes. Spectral analysis of radiation from these nuclei can help determine the vibrational modes of strings.
- **Computer Modeling:** Modeling the interaction of strings on cosmic scales can provide insights into the mechanisms of error correction and balancing planetary systems. Computer models can simulate the vibrational modes of strings and their interaction, providing valuable data for testing the theory.

Questions for Further Research

Our theory proposes new ideas that require further research and mathematical substantiation. Some of the questions that need further investigation include:

- **Mathematical Models:** It is necessary to develop mathematical models that accurately describe the interaction of extended strings. This will help test our assumptions and make the theory more precise.

- **Experimental Methods:** New experimental methods need to be developed to test the interaction of strings with particles and gravitational fields. This includes creating new detectors and data analysis techniques.
- **Research on Dark Matter:** Additional research on the nature of dark matter in the context of our theory is needed. This may include observations of galaxy clusters and the study of gravitational anomalies.
- **Study of Cosmic Anomalies:** It is necessary to study cosmic anomalies such as gravitational lenses and redshift in the context of string interaction. This can help determine the impact of strings on the structure of the Universe.

Conclusions

We have proposed a new concept that considers strings as large structures forming the foundation of the Universe. This theory explains the interaction of light and matter through the vibrational modes of strings, the role of black holes in information storage, and the stabilization of planetary systems. We have also considered possible experimental confirmations and questions for further research that can provide new insights into the structure and expansion of the Universe.

Our theory combines elements of quantum mechanics, general relativity, and modern concepts of dark matter, offering a new approach to understanding the fundamental structures and interactions in the cosmos. Further experiments and theoretical research can help confirm or refute these assumptions, opening new horizons in the study of the nature of light, matter, and the Universe as a whole.

It is worth noting that this theory is merely an idea that we aim to explore and develop further possibilities for advancement. I apologize if my ideas have shown my ignorance or lack of professionalism, but the ability to express an idea, even if it is purely theoretical, is the driving force behind many ideas and inventions that advance humanity.

I am sincerely grateful to those who will form their opinions and point out shortcomings. I am fully open to communication and discussion of ideas, as well as for further assistance in the development of this theory and practical experiments. I also want to express special thanks to the invaluable help of ChatGPT-4o, without which this paper would not have been written. Its support and assistance in the writing process were invaluable.